

Constraining dust properties in Circumstellar Envelopes of C-stars in the Small Magellanic Cloud: optical constants and grain size of carbon dust

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Abstract

We present our recent investigation aimed at constraining the typical size and optical properties of carbon dust grains in Circumstellar envelopes (CSEs) of carbon-rich stars (C-stars) in the Small Magellanic Cloud (SMC).

We applied our recent dust growth model, coupled with a radiative transfer code, to the dusty CSEs of C-stars along the TP-AGB phase, for which we computed spectra and colors. We then compared our modeled colors in the Near and Mid Infrared (NIR and MIR) bands with the observed ones, testing different assumptions in our dust scheme and employing different optical constants data sets for carbon dust. We constrained the optical properties of carbon dust by identifying the combinations of typical grain size and optical constants data set which simultaneously reproduce several colors in the NIR and MIR wavelengths. In particular, the different choices of optical properties and grain size lead to differences in the NIR and MIR colors greater than two magnitudes in some cases.

We concluded that the complete set of selected NIR and MIR colors are best reproduced by small grains, with sizes between 0.06 and 0.1 μm , rather than by large grains of 0.2-0.4 μm . The inability of large grains to reproduce NIR and MIR colors is found to be independent of the adopted optical data set and the deviations between models and observations tend to increase for increasing grain sizes. We also find a possible trend of the typical grain size with mass-loss and/or carbon-excess in the CSEs of these stars.

The work presented is preparatory to future studies aimed at calibrating the TP-AGB phase through resolved stellar populations in the framework of the STARKEY project.

1 Introduction

Nearby galaxies, and in particular the Magellanic Clouds (MCs), are ideal objects for detailed analysis of dusty carbon-rich stars. Photometric data of resolved stars in the SMC are now available in a wide range of wavelengths by the Two Micron All Sky Survey (2MASS, Skrutskie *et al.*, 2006) and by the Spitzer Survey of the Small Magellanic Cloud (S³MC, Bolatto *et al.*, 2007). The Spitzer Space Telescope Legacy Program “Surveying the Agents of Galaxy Evolution in the tidally stripped, low metallicity Small Magellanic Cloud” (SAGE-SMC, Gordon *et al.*, 2011) represents the most complete set of Infrared data in the range between 3.6-160 μm . From the resulting catalog, Boyer *et al.* (2011) were able to classify about 5800 TP-AGB stars in the SMC.

On the theoretical side, the standard stationary wind model coupled with dust growth, originally introduced by Gail & Sedlmayr (1999), has been recently coupled with the TP-AGB tracks (Zhukovska *et al.*, 2008; Ventura *et al.*, 2012; Di Criscienzo *et al.*, 2013), including our group (Nanni *et al.*, 2013, 2014). Our revised version of such a model, coupled with the updated TP-AGB tracks by Marigo *et al.* (2013), has been shown to successfully reproduce some important observed trends in solar-like environments, i.e. outflow expansion velocities vs the mass-loss rate, for both M- and C-stars (Nanni *et al.*, 2013).

In our latest work, we moved forward by performing radiative transfer calculations throughout the dusty CSE, calculating the stellar spectra and colors along the TP-AGB phase

(Nanni *et al.*, 2016). The colors obtained have been compared with the observed ones of C- and extreme-stars (x-stars) in the SMC (Boyer *et al.*, 2011). The majority of x-stars are likely to be carbon-rich (van Loon *et al.*, 1997, 2006, 2008; Matsuura *et al.*, 2009). We focused our comparisons on carbon-rich TP-AGBs, since these stars are the most relevant for the interpretation of NIR and MIR colors of the resolved population in many galaxies, including the ones in the MCs (Woods *et al.*, 2011; Riebel *et al.*, 2012).

The emerging spectra and colors obtained from our models, are shaped by the input optical constants of carbon dust and by the final grain size. This fact represents a critical point, because several optical data sets for carbon dust, quite different one from each other, are available in the literature (Andersen *et al.*, 1999). In addition to that, the typical size of carbon grains in CSEs of C-stars is rather uncertain. Since it is not possible to choose the most suitable combination of optical data set and grain size a priori, it is necessary to compare the results of the models with the detailed observations currently available. The dynamical effects produced by the choice of different carbon optical data sets has been studied by Andersen *et al.* (1999), while in Nanni *et al.* (2016) our group presented a systematic study in which the modelled colors computed along the TP-AGB tracks have been compared with a large number of C-stars in the SMC. The main novelty introduced in Nanni *et al.* (2016) consists in the systematic analysis of which combinations of optical data sets and grain sizes best reproduce most of the NIR and MIR colors simulta-

neously, without limiting the investigation to individual CCDs or color-magnitude diagrams (CMDs), as performed by other groups (Ventura *et al.*, 2014, 2016; Dell’Agli *et al.*, 2015b,a). The work presented has been preparatory to follow-up studies aimed at calibrating the TP-AGB phase through resolved stellar populations in star clusters and galaxies in the framework of the ERC project STARKEY.

2 Method

The dust formation scheme adopted, fully explained in Nanni *et al.* (2013, 2014), follows the dust production along the TP-AGB phase once the input stellar parameters, such as the effective temperature (T_{eff}), luminosity (L), actual stellar mass (M), mass-loss rate (\dot{M}) and initial elemental abundances in the atmosphere, are specified. The input stellar quantities are computed by means of the PARSEC code (Bressan *et al.*, 2012), coupled with the COLIBRI code (Marigo *et al.*, 2013). The final output of the dust growth model, for each set of input parameters, provides the dust chemistry, condensation fractions, grain size, dust condensation temperature and the outflow expansion velocity of the modelled CSE.

In our framework, dust grains are accreted on pre-existing refractive particles known as “seed nuclei”, which number is often assumed to be a free parameter of the model (Gail & Sedlmayr, 1999; Ferrarotti & Gail, 2006; Ventura *et al.*, 2012; Nanni *et al.*, 2013, 2014). In addition to that, in our computations the number of seed nuclei is scaled with the carbon-excess as:

$$\epsilon_{s,C} \propto \epsilon_s(\epsilon_C - \epsilon_O). \quad (1)$$

Under this assumption, for a given choice of the value of ϵ_s , the final grain size obtained is only mildly dependent on the variation of the stellar parameters along the TP-AGB tracks, as also found in the hydrodynamical calculations by Mattsson *et al.* (2010). The typical grain size computed through our simulations ranges between 0.035 and 0.7 μm for $-11 \leq \log(\epsilon_s) \leq -15.4$.

The radiative transfer calculations throughout the dusty CSEs have been performed by means of the code More of DUSTY (Groenewegen, 2012, MoD), based on DUSTY (Ivezic & Elitzur, 1997). The inputs for the radiative transfer calculations are taken from our dust model. In particular, we provide to More of DUSTY the monochromatic optical depth at $\lambda \sim 1 \mu\text{m}$ (τ_1), the dust temperature at the boundary of the dust formation zone (T_{inn}), and the final optical properties, which are derived from the data sets listed in Table 1. The photospheric input spectrum for each model along the TP-AGB tracks is obtained by interpolating in effective temperature (T_{eff}) and carbon excess the spectra available from the recent COMARCS grid (Aringer *et al.*, 2016). The tracks employed for the calibration have been chosen in a range of initial masses and metallicity values suitable for the SMC (Marigo & Girardi, 2007; Nanni *et al.*, 2016). The selected version of the TP-AGB tracks are the ones revised as explained in Rosenfield *et al.* (2014, 2016).

The deviations between our models and observations is quantified by a least square minimization by dividing the J – Ks range of the observed stars into five bins. The colors considered for the calibration are J – Ks, [3.6] – [8.0], J – [3.6], J – [8.0], Ks – [3.6] and Ks – [8.0] in the entire J – Ks range, plus [5.8] – [8.0] and [3.6] – [4.5] for stars dominated by dust emission (J – Ks ≥ 2.5). In fact, the spectra of less dust-rich stars are likely to be affected by C₃ absorp-

Table 1: Optical data sets for amC available in the literature.

Designation	$\rho_{d,\text{amC}}$ [g/cm ³]	Reference
Jaeger400	1.435	Jager <i>et al.</i> (1998)
Jaeger600	1.670	Jager <i>et al.</i> (1998)
Jaeger800	1.843	Jager <i>et al.</i> (1998)
Jaeger1000	1.988	Jager <i>et al.</i> (1998)
Zubko1	1.87	Zubko <i>et al.</i> (1996)
Zubko2	1.87	Zubko <i>et al.</i> (1996)
Zubko3	1.87	Zubko <i>et al.</i> (1996)
Rouleau	1.85	Rouleau & Martin (1991)
Hanner	1.85	Hanner (1988)

tion features between 4 and 6 μm (Sloan *et al.*, 2015), which are not well fitted by the available opacity data (see Fig. 10 of Jørgensen *et al.*, 2000). An observed star in a certain J – Ks color bin, occupies a given position in the space of parameters defined by the selected colors. Therefore, in each bin in J – Ks, we computed the average values of the colors of the observed stars. In each J – Ks bin and for each color, the deviation of the TP-AGB models from the average observed value, normalized by the dispersion of the observed data, $\sigma_{c,\text{obs}}$, is:

$$\sigma_c = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{\text{model}} \left(\frac{x_{\text{model}} - x_{\text{av}}}{\sigma_{c,\text{obs}}} \right)^2}{N_{\text{model}}}}. \quad (2)$$

The deviation for all the colors of our simulations is:

$$\sigma = \frac{\sum_c \sigma_c}{N_c}. \quad (3)$$

A good agreement between models and observations is obtained for small values of σ which should not be too larger than ~ 1 .

3 Results

The different choices of the carbon optical data set and grain size lead to sizable differences in the colors consider, which are greater than two magnitudes in some cases. As an example, we show in Fig. 1 the final J – Ks color as a function of the grain size for different choices of the optical data sets. The radiative transfer calculations have been performed changing only the grain size and optical data set. We adopted an input spectrum with $T_{\text{eff}} = 3000 \text{ K}$, C/O ~ 1.4 and an initial set of metallicity typical of the SMC. The dust temperature at the boundary of the dust formation zone is fixed at $T_{\text{inn}} = 1000 \text{ K}$. The optical depth at 1 μm , $\tau_1 = 10$, which corresponds to a dust-enshrouded C-star. As can be appreciated from Fig. 1, the colors obtained by only changing the optical and grain size, can change up to four order of magnitudes in the most extreme cases. The large differences obtained in the colors for different choices of the optical data set and grain sizes indicate again the need for a calibration of these quantities.

The calibration of the optical data set and grain sizes, turns out to be a challenging task, because of the difficulty of reproducing the selected colors at the same time. In fact, a specific combination of optical data set and grain size can produce a good agreement in a certain CCD but might perform very poorly in another one. We show this effect in Fig. 2, where

Figure 1: $J - K_s$ color as a function of the grain size for selected data sets of amorphous carbon dust. The models are computed for $\tau_1 = 10$.

we plotted two different CCDs, $J - K_s$ vs $J - [3.6]$ (upper panel) and $J - K_s$ vs $[3.6] - [8.0]$ (lower panel), for the same combination of optical data sets and grain size. Even if the observed trend in the $J - K_s$ vs $J - [3.6]$ CCD appears to be fairly well reproduced by the models, the agreement is not as good in the $J - K_s$ vs $[3.6] - [8.0]$ CCD. For this reason, it is essential to reproduce the largest number of colors simultaneously.

The comparison between the models along the TP-AGB tracks and the observations is summarized in Fig. 3, where $\langle \sigma \rangle$ is the deviation computed through Eq. 2 and 3, averaged for all the bins in $J - K_s$. The quantity $\langle \sigma \rangle$ is plotted as a function of the grain size and for different optical data sets. Fig. 3 shows which combinations of optical data sets and grain sizes best reproduce the observed colors in the entire range of $J - K_s$. In particular, the value of $\langle \sigma \rangle$ tends to increase as a function of the grain size. Therefore, the observed stars are best reproduced by small grains of $a_{\text{amc}} \leq 0.1 \mu\text{m}$, where the exact value of a_{amc} depends on the specific optical data set considered. For $a_{\text{amc}} \geq 0.2 \mu\text{m}$ the discrepancy between models and observations becomes considerable $\langle \sigma \rangle \geq 1.5$. Some of the optical data sets are never able to reproduce the observations (Zubko3 and Jaeger600). In Fig. 4 we plot some examples of optical data sets and grain sizes which are in poor (upper panel) and good (lower panel) agreement with observations. As previously discussed, all the well performing combinations of optical data sets and grain sizes are obtained for small grain sizes of $a_{\text{amc}} \leq 0.12 \mu\text{m}$, while large grains never show a good agreement with observations.

The analysis performed, also suggest a possible trend between the mass-loss rate and/or the carbon excess with the grain size, with smaller and more numerous dust grains for redder stars. This trend is particularly evident from the analysis of the optical data set of Rouleau & Martin (1991), as shown in Fig. 3. In this figure, the quantity σ from Eq. 2 is plotted as a function of the $J - K_s$ color and it shows the trend of σ for increasingly dust-enshrouded stars. The optical data

Figure 2: $J - K_s$ vs $J - [3.6]$ CCD (upper panel) and $J - K_s$ vs $[3.6] - [8.0]$ CCD (lower panel) for the observed sample of C- (red pentagons) and x-stars (open green circles). The observed points have been superimposed with the average value of models obtained with a given combination of optical data set and grain size, listed in the top left. Full blue circles represent the average values of the observed stars in different $J - K_s$ intervals.

Figure 3: Deviations between models and observations as a function of the grain size, for different combinations optical data sets available in the literature. The value of $\langle \sigma \rangle$ is the average of σ in all the bins.

set by Rouleau & Martin (1991) produces a good agreement between models and observations in the entire $J - K_s$ range with $a_{\text{amc}} \sim 0.12 \mu\text{m}$, except for the reddest bin, in which the best agreement is achieved by decreasing the grain size down to $a_{\text{amc}} \sim 0.06 \mu\text{m}$.

4 Conclusions

We put some astrophysical constraints on the sets of carbonaceous dust grain optical properties found in the literature, by coupling our TP-AGB models (Bressan *et al.*, 2012; Marigo *et al.*, 2013; Rosenfield *et al.*, 2014, 2016) with dust formation (Nanni *et al.*, 2013, 2014) and a radiative transfer code (Groenewegen, 2012). In particular, in Nanni *et al.* (2016) we systematically analyzed the performance of the different combination of optical data sets and grain sizes by comparing our modelled NIR and MIR colors along the TP-AGB tracks with the ones observed for C-stars in the SMC (Boyer *et al.*, 2011).

We notice that for red stars, $\tau_1 = 10$, the variations in the colors computed with different combinations of optical data sets and grain sizes can be considerable (up to four magnitudes).

Using a least squares minimization method, we derived the combinations of optical data sets and grain sizes that simultaneously provide the best agreement with observations for several colors. The colors included in our calibration are best reproduced by small grains of $0.035 \leq a_{\text{amc}} \leq 0.12 \mu\text{m}$ rather than by large ones $a_{\text{amc}} \geq 0.2 \mu\text{m}$. In particular, large grains are never able to reproduce the colors considered in the analysis, independently of the optical data set adopted. Some of the combinations of data sets and grain sizes well comparing with observations in a specific CCD, can yield a poor agreement in other CCDs. Focusing on the models computed with the optical data set by Rouleau & Martin (1991), we obtain that dust of $a_{\text{amc}} \sim 0.12 \mu\text{m}$ well reproduce the observed colors in the entire range of $J - K_s$, except for the reddest bin

Figure 4: $J - K_s$ vs $K_s - [3.6]$ CCDs for the observed sample C-stars coded as in Fig. 2. The two panels are superimposed with the average value of models which produce a bad (upper panel) or good (lower panel) agreement with the observations. The different combinations of optical data sets and grain sizes are listed in the top-left of each panel.

Figure 5: Deviations between observed data and models computed with the optical data set by Rouleau & Martin (1991) through Eqs. 2 and 3 as a function of the $J - K_s$ color. Two choices of the typical grain size $a_{\text{amC}} \sim 0.12$ and $0.06 \mu\text{m}$ are shown.

(with $J - K_s \geq 4$). For these heavily dust-enshrouded objects, the best agreement with observations is obtained for smaller dust grains of $a_{\text{amC}} \sim 0.06 \mu\text{m}$. This behaviour suggests a possible inverse trend between the carbon grain size and the mass-loss rate and/or the carbon excess.

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